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Report on the integrated use of QSAR and TTC approaches to prioritise chemicals for further risk assessment in the context of mixtures

WP 2– QSAR and TTC approaches for setting test priorities

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Report on the integrated use of QSAR and TTC approaches to prioritise chemicals for further risk assessment in the context of mixtures

October 2018

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Report on the integrated use of QSAR and TTC approaches to prioritise chemicals for further risk assessment in the context of mixtures

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Abstract

This deliverable describes the overall workflow followed in EuroMix Work Package 2. This workflow, which is proposed to be used as a first tier *in-silico* risk assessment of chemical mixtures in general, consists of four steps:

- 1) The first step is the identification of chemicals in food or feed that are of interest for combined exposures. A list of 1598 substances has been identified specifically for the purpose of EuroMix, and is described in D2.1 “Report describing cumulative assessment groups for a broad range of chemicals, based on information extracted from (literature) databases”. This list – the EuroMix Chemical Inventory – is subsequently completed with the results from the *in-silico* tools and calculations performed in EuroMix Work Package 2, described in detail in Deliverables 2.2, 2.3 and this deliverable (see next steps).
- 2) Determining the probability that a chemical belongs to a certain Cumulative Assessment Group (CAG). The level at which CAGs need to be determined for mixture risk assessment (level 1: organ toxicity, level 2: organ effect phenotype, level 3: mode of action, i.e. cellular processes, and level 4: mechanism of action, or molecular initiating events) is not established yet, as indications for this should come from the experimental work packages in EuroMix. The present deliverable D2.4 outlines the work-flows using existing QSAR models described in EuroMix D2.2 (Report on the use of *in-silico* methods for the prioritisation of substances and mixtures thereof), in combination with the results from detailed molecular docking calculations performed as new research in the EuroMix project and described in D2.3.
- 3) Assignment of a relative potency factor to each chemical that was considered in the previous step to be part of the CAG of interest. These relative potencies are used to scale the exposures of all mixture components. RPF derivation using Threshold of Toxicological Concern (TTC) concepts, and Molecular Docking results were described in D2.3. Additionally a proposal for the use of read across based on chemical similarity is given in this deliverable. Interpretation of molecular docking based RPFs, as well as the interpretation of *in vitro* modelling results from WP3 in EuroMix, requires In Vitro to In Vivo Extrapolation. A first (QSAR based) tier to IVIVE is presented in section 6 of this deliverable.
- 4) Finally the mixture risk is determined by adding up all the scaled exposures of the mixture components that are predicted to be part of the Cumulative Assessment Group. As exposure considerations are not taken into account at all at this stage – for a large part of the EuroMix Inventory no exposure data will be available – the final risk assessment calculations are not part of this Deliverable.

This workflow and all the data obtained with the tools and model predictions will be implemented in the EuroMix software tool as part of the EuroMix Work Package 6. The individual tools used in the mixture risk assessment workflow can be used to do prioritizations and rankings, i.e. to find the (predicted) most potent substances for a specific CAG. In section 5 of this Deliverable, these prioritizations have been performed to generate lists of potentially interesting substances - based on their predicted effect / mechanism of action and potency – for further testing in the *in-vitro* toolbox (EuroMix work package 3).

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1. Introduction

In order to make a lower tier estimate of any mixture toxicity, the simplest approach is to assume full dose additivity of all the individual components in the mixture. Although cases of *synergism* have been described in literature, these seem to be restricted to isolated exceptional cases, e.g. involving substances that have complementary agonistic and antagonistic behaviour for endocrine receptors. Even in that area (endocrine disruption) descriptions of true synergistic toxicological behaviour are scarce or not convincing. Grosso modo it can be assumed that dose additivity is a realistic approach. If co-exposure in time is considered this lower tier approach to mixture toxicity risk assessment becomes even more precautionary or conservative.

One refinement to (overall) dose additivity is to address risk assessment of mixtures (or co-exposures) at the level of Cumulative Assessment Groups (CAGs) as proposed by EFSA [EFSA 2013]. The idea is that effects from chemicals acting on different organs would not be directly additive. Some damage to one organ (e.g. liver) would not necessarily “add up” to some damage already done to another organ (e.g. kidneys). This might hold true especially at low exposure levels. The levels at which substance effects should be grouped in this approach is open for debate, but 4 levels are distinguished by EFSA:

- Level 1: organ effects (e.g. liver toxicity, developmental toxicity);
- Level 2: phenomenological effect (e.g. steatosis or necrosis as a phenomenological effect in liver toxicity);
- Level 3: mode of action (e.g. cellular processes that can be determined by in vitro assays, such as accumulation triglycerides in the liver cell);
- Level 4: mechanism of action (e.g. specific (nuclear) receptor interactions linked to a certain pathway of toxicity).

In task 2.2, methodology has been explored to determine Cumulative Assessment Group (CAG) memberships, based on chemical structure alone. EuroMix Deliverable 2.2 describes the application of existing (Quantitative) Structure-Activity ((Q)SAR) and/or Molecular Docking models to indicate whether a certain chemical can exert a specific toxicological effect or not. The procedure proposed in EuroMix Deliverable 2.2 (“Report on the use of in-silico methods for the prioritisation of substances and mixtures thereof”) predicts whether a certain effect will be likely to occur upon exposure to a specific substance, but it does however not give any information on the potency, or dose at which this effect is thought to occur. This potency information is also needed to allow calculation of a quantitative measure of mixture risk.

In classical toxicology, the potency of a chemical is derived from *in-vivo* studies and is based on reference doses such the No Observed Adverse Effect Levels (NOAEL) or the lower confidence limit of the benchmark dose (BMDL) (from a long term toxicity study, if risk assessment is performed for chronic risk). By taking

the ratio of the NOAELs relative to one well-studied reference compound, one can derive *relative* potency factors (RPFs). These RPFs are used to express exposure in toxicological units that can easily be summed to an overall estimate of the cumulative exposure.

In the absence of *in-vivo* toxicity data it is needed to derive a (worst case) proxy estimate of a NOAEL for these compounds, which can be used to derive a first tier relative potency factor for the cumulative risk assessment of a mixture. For this purpose, the concept of Threshold of Toxicological Concern (TTC) was considered a good first tier, but truly worst case, approach. This was described in EuroMix D2.3 (“Report on the use of the Threshold of Toxicological Concern (TTC) for the prioritization of substances and mixtures thereof”).

For all the chemicals of the EuroMix Inventory (Deliverable 2.1), TTCs were calculated as a first tier (worst case) estimate of proxy NOAELs. The TTC concept relies on the evaluation of a large set of *in-vivo* long term toxicity studies and the *lowest* NOAEL that could be derived from these studies. The underlying assumption of the TTC concept is that the NOAELs coming from this evaluation will show a (log) normal distribution, allowing for determination of e.g. the 1st, 5th or 10th percentile from this distribution as a starting point for the derivation of a *generally* applicable threshold where no effect is to be expected from more than 1, 5 or 10% of the substances. In the original TTC concept an assessment factor of 100 is applied to the 5th percentile to assure that no effect is expected for any substance. For the purpose of generating proxy NOAELs to derive a RPF in EuroMix, the 5th percentile of the distribution is proposed to be used directly, without applying the additional assessment factor of 100.

Apart from the use of TTC for a first approach to estimate a worst case proxy NOAEL, also molecular docking models are a promising tool as they provide quantitative results (receptor binding energies). Therefore, potency factors may be derived based on these binding energies. A procedure to perform this translation of binding energy to (relative) potency is briefly indicated in D2.3 as well. (More advanced molecular dynamics analysis can even be used to distinguish agonistic from antagonistic potencies).

In this deliverable we describe the possibility to use all the *in silico* tools jointly to perform prioritization within one or more CAGs, following the consecutive steps in the process of cumulative risk assessment: a) establishing reference datasets - section 2, b) determining CAG memberships – section 3, c) deriving RPF estimates – section 4, and d) and applying the integrated concept to perform prioritizations – section 5.

Additionally, a first attempt to define a QSAR based *generic* Physiologically Based Toxicokinetics (PBTK) modelling approach is described in section 6.

2. Lists and databases, from previous WP2 deliverables

The chemicals of the EuroMix Chemical Inventory and the toxicity database produced in Task 2.1 were subjected to the *in-silico* methods explored previously in EuroMix D2.2 and 2.3.

Chemicals were run through different software models to generate QSAR predictions for the three selected endpoints in EuroMix (hepatotoxicity, developmental toxicity, endocrine disruption). These QSAR models, their statistical performance and the results are detailed in EuroMix Deliverable 2.2. Detailed results can be found in the In Silico Toxicity Predictions Database v5_18092018. A summary of all the results (0/1, active/inactive) is given for the whole Euromix Chemical Inventory of 1598 substances in Annex II to this Deliverable.

Determination of the correct TTC for the 1598 substances in the Inventory is described in EuroMix Deliverable 2.3. The assigned TTC values are included as mixture component properties in the EuroMix Software tool (work package 6) and will be available in the EuroMix software tool as very first, worst case proxy NOAELs to determine RPFs. The results of the TTC proxy NOAEL assignment are in Annex II to this Deliverable.

Molecular Docking calculations have been performed for the whole Euromix Inventory for a series of Nuclear Receptor models that are involved in the hepatotoxicity/steatosis pathway, and for estrogen and androgen receptors (endocrine disruption). The results of these docking calculations are also included as calculated binding energies in Annex II to this Deliverable.

For all calculations two dimensional structures were needed as input to the software; these were taken from the EuroMix inventory as well, with the derivation of the chemical structures described in detail in EuroMix deliverable 2.2. For the molecular docking simulations the 2D structure used as input was converted to an energy optimized 3D structure.

3. Determining CAG membership using *in-silico* tools

3.1 Existing QSARs – CAG membership decision schemes

Hepatotoxicity

There were 10 existing QSAR models for the endpoint hepatotoxicity identified (EuroMix D2.2), specifically

- COSMOS LXR binding model using Padel descriptors---not used in majority consensus (WoE) predictions
- COSMOS Nuclear Receptor model
- DEREK Nexus
- MULTICASE Hepatotoxicity module
- OCHEM AhR model
- OCHEM PPARgamma model
- OECD QSAR Toolbox HESS alert
- PaDEL-DD Predictor
- Pizzo structural alert model
- FERA Pizzo QSAR model
- Additionally the University of Milano generated binding energies using molecular docking models for 16 liver nuclear receptors (see section 3.3) which are used as an additional indicator for hepatotoxicity/steatosis

The specifics of each models are described and referenced in D2.2.

To decide whether a substance belongs to the CAG hepatotoxicity a consensus approach is applied using the *in silico* models mentioned above except the COSMOS LXR binding model (based on PADEL descriptors) which appeared to have a sensitivity of almost zero, So a total of 10 models (the molecular docking models wer considered as one type of model) was used in the majority weight of evidence. In this majority consensus decision model the results are interpreted as follows: if 5 or more models out of 10 predict a substance to be hepatotoxic, the substance is considered to be part of the CAG hepatotoxicity. This ≥ 5 out of 10 rule (or more generally stated: $\geq 50\%$ of the applicable models for a certain toxicological endpoint) yielded the best balance between sensitivity and specificity and the highest accuracy for reproducing the CAG level 1 assignment as determined by EFSA for liver toxicity.

The amount of positive QSAR results required to label a substance as member of the CAG can be changed for different purposes. If a less conservative approach is used, each component with only one positive

QSAR prediction could be included in the CAG. Drawback of such an approach is the (very) high number of false positive results, and the subsequent overestimation of the mixture risk.

Steatosis

For the level 2 CAG liver steatosis, 5 relevant QSAR models were selected as informative (and predictive) to assign substances to the Level 2 CAG of steatosis, as a subgroup within the Level 1 CAG of hepatotoxicity. These selected models were the DEREK Steatosis Alert, OCHEM AhR activators, OCHEM PPAR γ agonists, COSMOS LXR activators, and the COSMOS Nuclear Receptor model. The statistics of the COSMOS LXR model did not show selectivity (accuracy was 50%, with almost 0% sensitivity in the dedicated steatosis reference dataset, see next section 3.2), therefore this QSAR model was omitted. To assign a substance to this liver steatosis CAG, the following rule of thumb was used (giving the highest accuracy, see Annex III): A substance should have ≥ 2 out of the 4 steatosis related QSAR models predicting positive, AND at least one of molecular docking binding energies calculated by the University of Milano is below the threshold for receptor binding (-6.5 kcal/mol) AND the overall prediction of hepatotoxicity is positive (i.e. $\geq 50\%$ of the applicable hepatotoxicity QSARs predicts positive, as described above)..

Developmental toxicity

For developmental toxicity, 4 existing QSAR models were identified: DEREK Nexus, VEGA Caesar QSAR model, VEGA PG Library model, TEST Developmental toxicity model (also see Euromix D2.2). Again a simple consensus model was applied to this battery of QSARs, i.e. if $\geq 50\%$ of the applicable models predicts positive, we assume the component has to be included in the CAG developmental toxicity. For this CAG, no specific QSAR models could be identified that would allow a refined prediction of the specific phenotype cranio-facial malformations. Therefore, only predictions at level 1 of the CAG developmental toxicity are available.

Endocrine disruption, with focus on anti-androgenic effects

For endocrine disruption focus was upon anti-androgenicity (e.g. decreased ano-genital distance) as an adverse endpoint. Available models are QSAR models that predict the interaction with the estrogen and the androgen receptors. For the estrogen receptor 8 different QSAR models are available (DEREK Nexus, Estrogen Receptor binding alert in the OECD QSAR Toolbox, rTER Expert system, DART scheme, VEGA RBA QSAR Model, COSMOS Nuclear Receptor Model, OCHEM Estrogen receptor alpha agonists model 2, VEGA CERAPP). Based on the results from the EuroMix Molecular Docking calculations for the estrogen receptor an additional model was added to make a total of 9 models. The consensus model is again using the $\geq 50\%$ of the applicable models predict positive rule as a criterion for distinguishing estrogen binding substances

from those that are estrogen non-binders. For the androgen receptor 4 QSAR models (OCHEM Androgen agonists models 1-3, COSMOS AR alert) are available. Based on the result from the Euromix molecular docking calculations for the androgen receptor, an additional model was added, making a total of 5 predictive models. The consensus model criterion used in this case is $\geq 40\%$ of the QSAR models positive ($\geq 2/5$ models) for prediction of a substance as androgen receptor binding.

Furthermore, one molecular docking model is applied (see EuroMix D2.2) for the aromatase inhibition, which is also considered a pathway potentially involved in endocrine disruption.

If any of these pathways is predicted to be modulated (i.e. estrogen, androgen OR aromatase), the substance is considered as potentially endocrine disrupting, and therefore part of the CAG endocrine disruption. As there is no consensus reference data set of endocrine disruptors, there are no performance statistics for this endpoint. Complicating factor is that the models predict the potential activation of an endocrine mechanism, but they do not predict an adverse effect in a whole organism, which forms the second requirement in the definitions by o.a. WHO and EU for an endocrine disruptor. The first requirement is mechanistic evidence of an endocrine pathway involved.

The results from these 4 CAG membership decision schemes, as well as the individual qualitative results from the QSAR models (expressed as '0' or '1') are given for the whole EuroMix Inventory in Annex II to this deliverable. The data and the decision schemes will be included in the EuroMix Software tool (WP6) in order to allow a user to make CAG membership selections for substances where this is not supported by *in-vivo* data.

3.2 Approach to derive a fit-for-purpose QSAR model for Steatosis

At the EuroMix Consortium meeting in Ghent (October 2017) predictions for steatosis were available using a subset of the selected (Q)SAR models for hepatotoxicity (Derek steatosis alerts, COSMOS NR model, OCHEM AhR and PPARg models). These models gave additional information that could be related to and/or used as a prediction of steatosis as (one of) the effects leading to hepatotoxicity. For example, DEREK alerts for hepatotoxicity all have a detailed description including the phenotype of effects seen in substances having that specific alert. This allows us to make a sub selection of DEREK substructure alerts that should be predictive of the phenotype steatosis.

Furthermore, molecular docking models for 16 liver nuclear receptors associated with steatosis were developed in the EuroMix project, and the calculated binding energies could be used as predictors of

(potential) steatosis as a phenotype of effect. However, there was no consensus on how to test their accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, or to determine adequate threshold values for the binding energies to distinguish between steatosis positive and steatosis negative compounds.

In order to better determine predictive statistical performance of the existing QSAR models, and to determine adequate threshold values for molecular docking binding energies, a steatosis validation set has been compiled. This dataset comprises pharmaceuticals known to be positive/negative for steatosis in human studies (Donato et al. 2012; Benet et al. 2014; Jennings et al. 2014; Tolosa et al. 2016), PPPs from the EFSA CAG steatosis (mammals, as documented in the EFSA supporting publications on CAG Liver toxicity, and in EuroMix D2.1 the toxicity database) and from Al Eryani et al. 2015 (*in-vitro* studies). This validation set, consisting of 207 compounds (103 positives, 104 negatives), is given in Annex III to this deliverable.

Cooper statistics (accuracy, sensitivity and specificity) for the 4 QSAR models that give information on steatosis as an effect as well as the consensus model using the majority vote from the 4 models are:

Model	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity
Derek Steatosis Alert	0.52	0.13	0.91
OCHEM AhR binding	0.57	0.52	0.63
OCHEM PPARg binding	0.55	0.45	0.64
COSMOS NR model	0.55	0.73	0.38
COSMOS LXR-binding	0.50	0.06	0.93
Consensus (2 or more of 4 QSAR positive)	0.60	0.63	0.57

The COSMOS LXR binding model had an accuracy of 50% and a sensitivity of only 6% and was therefore not regarded further for the battery approach. As the statistics for predicting steatosis, and assigning a substance to the level 2 CAG Steatosis of the remaining models are also not very good, it was decided that in the last year of the EuroMix project Work Package 2 will aim to derive, using the steatosis validation set, a specific fit-for-purpose QSAR model predicting CAG membership for the level 2 phenotype steatosis. This steatosis QSAR model is a binary classification model built using the TANAGRA platform and is based on 4 chemical descriptors. The first indications are that predictive performance of such a model would give an accuracy around 70%, whereas the best accordance for any of the QSAR or docking models, either stand alone or in batteries, so far did not exceed ~60%. New QSAR model derivation was never part of the

EuroMix project proposal, but with the effort of assembling a good reference dataset already performed, it is thought to be a useful extra activity. Results will be reported in a specific publication in an international scientific journal, giving credit to the EU H2020 project EuroMix.

3.3 Molecular Docking

For all the substances in the EuroMix Inventory, molecular docking calculations have been performed using an array of receptor models that were deemed relevant for the three endpoints in EuroMix.

For hepatotoxicity and steatosis, the following list consisting of 16 liver nuclear receptors models was constructed: Aryl hydrocarbon Receptor (AhR), the Constitutive Androstane Receptor (CAR), Farnesoid X Receptor (FXR), the Glucocorticoid Receptor (GR), Liver X Receptor alpha and beta (LXR α , β), Peroxisome Proliferator-activation Receptor alpha, beta and gamma (PPAR α , β , γ), Pregnane X Receptor (PXR), the Retinoic Acid Receptor alpha, beta and gamma (RAR α , β , γ) and the Retinoic X Receptor alpha, beta and gamma (RXR α , β , γ).

Binding energies for these liver nuclear receptors were calculated for all 1598 compounds of the EuroMix Inventory, selecting the Triangle Matcher placement algorithm and using the London dG empirical scoring function for sorting the binding poses. The 30 top-scoring poses were refined through molecular mechanics, considering the receptor as a rigid body, and the refined complexes were scored through the GBVI/WSA dG empirical scoring function, selecting the five top-scoring poses and estimating their dissociation constant from the GBVI/WSA dG binding free energy values. The calculated binding energies are included in Annex II to this Deliverable.

For developmental toxicity and cranial malformation, AhR is seen as relevant, as well as the retinoic acid receptors RAR α , RAR β and RAR γ . Furthermore, Cyp26 is involved in some pathways, but no receptor binding data was created for this receptor in the EuroMix project as establishing a new docking model was too cost intensive for the WP2/University of Milano budget.

For endocrine disruption, binding energies for the (human) Estrogen Receptor alpha (ER α) and beta (ER β), the Androgen receptor (AR) as well as the Progesterone receptor (PR) were calculated following the same procedures as for the nuclear receptor selected tasked with hepatotoxicity and steatosis.

Threshold values for binding energies that would be sufficient to activate a receptor were set to -6.5 kcal/mol, based on rules of thumb and experience from pharmaceutical hit/lead identification [Eberini et al., 2015]. A statistical optimization for prediction of steatosis using the reference dataset constructed

within the EuroMix project (section 3.2) gives optimal threshold values for the binding energies between -6.5 and -6.8 Kcal/mol, which is very nice in line with the rules of thumb and previous experiences from Eberini et al. [2015].

3.4 Molecular Docking and Mechanisms of Action

The molecular docking results have been used to classify chemicals of the EuroMix Inventory into mechanism of actions (EFSA CAG level 4, the Molecular Initiating Event (MIE) in the Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP). The classification is based on the EuroMix AOP for liver steatosis, as established in Work Package 8.

A graphical representation of this AOP, together with a number of *in-vitro* assays available to measure key events in this AOP is given in the following figure:

The AOP starts with interaction of chemicals with a number of with liver nuclear receptors (Molecular Initiating Events, or MIEs), for which docking models were created within EuroMix. Using the established

threshold for binding (-6.5 kCal/mol) it can be determined for each component in the EuroMix Inventory, which pathway would potentially be triggered. Five different modes of action and their corresponding mechanisms of action can be distinguished in this AOP representation:

<u>Mechanisms of action</u>	<u>Mode of action</u>
1. PPARa antagonism	→ beta-oxidation inhibition
2. LXR, PXR, PPARg, FXR, GR and/or CAR stimulation	→ increase of fatty acid synthesis
3. LXR, PXR, PPARg, AhR agonism	→ increase of fatty acid influx
4. RAR agonism	→ direct stimulation of liver triglyceride accumulation
5. <u>Non-Nuclear receptor initiated MoA's</u>	→ unknown

Currently, there are still some difficulties in distinguishing the contribution of each potential component to these mechanisms of action and modes of action. First, molecular docking calculations do not predict receptor activation. It is assumed that better binding to a receptor directly leads to increased activation of that receptor, but this is not necessarily true. Currently, we cannot distinguish agonism (stimulation) from antagonism (inhibition), so that specifically PPARa antagonism is not adequately predicted. For practical reasons, we assume that binding equally result in agonism and/or antagonism.

Another uncertainty is that MoA2 (increased fatty acid synthesis) and MoA3 (increased fatty acid influx) have quite a bit of overlap, as LXR, PXR and PPARg stimulation would trigger both these mechanisms of action. The question is whether these are really distinguishable as different mechanisms of action.

Furthermore, it can also be questioned whether RAR really represents a separate mechanism of action, distinguishing it from those of MoA2 and MoA3, or that downstream processes following RAR (and the closely related Retinoid X Receptor; RXR) stimulation are just not known in sufficient detail yet.

It is also still an open question whether combinations of NR are required to trigger a mechanism (specifically MoA2 and/or MoA3) or that one single NR is sufficient.

Nonetheless, we used the approach for a first classification of the EuroMix Chemical Inventory compounds in groups with different MoAs, which can be updated once new information becomes available. For this, we assume that a single receptor that binds stronger than the cut-off value of -6.5 kCal/mol triggers (activates) the related Modes of Action.

In this way, the 5 different mechanisms of actions for steatosis have been assigned to the 1598 components in the EuroMix Inventory, as given in Annex II to this Deliverable. The assigned modes allow to make separate risk assessments for combinations of substances that have dissimilar mode of action, in the case that dose-addition would not be the appropriate assumption for mixture risk assessment.

From work performed *in vitro* and their verification *in vivo* (WP 3 and 4 of EuroMix) the question has to be answered whether these different modes of action (level 3 CAGs) or mechanisms of action (Level 4 CAGs) are dose additive or can be considered non-dose additive. The first results from WP3 with the *in-vitro* assays seem to indicate that the different modes of action are still fully dose additive, i.e. distinguishing components at CAG levels below the phenotype / level 2, is not giving any refinement of the risk assessment, for the organ endpoint hepatotoxicity/phenotype steatosis.

4. Estimating Relative Potencies when *in-vivo* data is absent

4.1 TTC based RPF derivation

Due to the nature of the TTC approach, it provides three different NOAEL surrogates, i.e. three different potencies. The TTC derivation scheme, (EFSA 2012, 2016a, 2016b) with the appropriate TTC values for the different classes is given below:

It should be noted that there are a large number of exceptions when the TTC concept is considered not-applicable, mainly due 1) to concerns that toxicity CAN occur at lower doses - e.g. endocrine substances, nano-forms of specific materials, high-potency mutagens, 2) substance classes not-, or under-represented in the original Munro database used to derive the TTC values - e.g. metallo-organic compounds, metals, inorganics, or 3) substances that might exert long term effects due to bioaccumulative behaviour, leading to substantially higher internal concentrations over longer time courses than can be expected based on the exposure duration in the toxicology testing performed to derive the TTC values. All these exceptions have to be taken into account when applying the TTC concept in the EuroMix workflow.

The classes “genotoxic carcinogens” and “organo-phosphates and –carbamates” with their respective TTC values are not applicable to the EuroMix workflow, as both effects are not relevant for the case studies in EuroMix (liver toxicity and steatosis, developmental toxicity and endocrine disruption). Furthermore, the EFSA opinions prescribe to group Cramer class II substances (moderate toxicity, TTC 540 ug/person/day) with the Cramer class III (high toxicity, TTC 90 ug/person/day) and use only the more conservative value of 90 ug/person/day for both Cramer classes, as the separation between the two classes is (statistically) not very strong. In the EuroMix workflow, we do distinguish Cramer class II substances as a separate class, and we apply the original 5th percentile as derived by Munro (Munro, 1996) for this class.

Furthermore, the derived TTC values include a safety factor of 100, which is applied to the 5th percentile of the NOEL distribution. In the EuroMix workflow, missing NOAEL values from *in-vivo* experiments have to be replaced with a *realistic worst case* estimate of the NOAEL. Hence, we do not apply the derived TTC, but instead use the 5th percentile of the NOEL distributions directly (without the extra safety factor of 100 applied). The ToxTree version 3.1.0.1851 software has been applied to determine the appropriate Cramer Class for all of the 1598 compounds in the EuroMix Chemical Inventory, using the Revised Cramer Decision Tree. The Cramer Class derivation is given for the whole Euromix Chemical Inventory in Annex II of this deliverable, together with the associated TTC-based NOAEL for the three classes:

Class III (High toxicity): TTC 90 ug/person/d = 1.5 ug/kg bw/d → 5th percentile NOAEL = **0.15 mg/kg bw/d**

Class II (Medium tox.): TTC 540 ug/person/d = 9 ug/kg bw/d → 5th percentile NOAEL = **0.9 mg/kg bw/d**

Class I (Low toxicity): TTC 1800 ug/person/d = 30 ug/kg bw/d → 5th percentile NOAEL = **3 mg/kg bw/d**

4.2 Effect Specific TTC approach

To refine the classical TTC approach, which is based on evaluation of all toxicological endpoints, an effect-specific TTC approach is worked out quantitatively for one group of substances (PPP, steatosis CAG). Instead of deriving the 5th percentile of the NOELs using any endpoint, the 5th percentile is derived using the distribution of NOELs *for the effect of steatosis*. This is described and illustrated in EuroMix Deliverable 2.3. For 98 substances that were actually showing Steatosis as an effect in the database of ~400 pesticides [EuroMix Toxicity Database, Deliverable D2.1], the 5th percentile of the NOAELs for Steatosis is estimated to be 0.5 mg/kg bw/day. This value should be compared to the original Munroe derived 5th percentile for the Cramer class III substances of 0.15 mg/kg bw/day, as the 98 PPPs showing steatosis almost all belong to this class. Thus, the effect-specific approach (only) leads to a 5th percentile which is a factor of 3.33 higher than the original value derived by Munroe. We think we can assume that this factor is a minimum factor for the difference in NOAEL for any effect or for steatosis specifically, and can be applied to the 5th percentiles derived from the Cramer class I and II substances as well. That would lead to Steatosis TTC-based NOAEL values of 2.7 mg/kg bw/day for Cramer class II and a value of 9 mg/kg bw/day for the Cramer class I compounds. Application of this same factor of 3.33 to other endpoints then hepatotoxicity is already more tentative and cannot be endorsed. The Steatosis specific TTC-based associated NOAELs then are:

Class III (High toxicity): Steatosis TTC-based NOAEL = 3.33 x 5th percentile NOAEL = **0.5 mg/kg bw/d**

Class II (Medium tox.): Steatosis TTC-based NOAEL = 3.33 x 5th percentile NOAEL = **3 mg/kg bw/d**

Class I (Low toxicity): Steatosis TTC-based NOAEL = 3.33 x 5th percentile NOAEL = **10 mg/kg bw/d**

These Steatosis-TTC-based replacement NOAELs are also given in Annex II with this Deliverable for the whole EuroMix Chemical Inventory. These NOAELs can subsequently be used to calculate Relative Potency Factors (RPFs), relative to a well studied substance, by dividing the NOAEL (in vivo) of the reference substance by these TTC-based NOAELs:

$$\text{RPF} = \frac{\text{NOAEL}(\textit{reference substance})}{\text{TTC-based NOAEL}(\textit{unknown substance})}$$

4.3 The use of Molecular Docking Binding Energies to estimate Relative Potency Factors

To further refine predictions of potency, the calculated binding energies from molecular docking were used. The results from computer based molecular docking analysis are reported in a binding energy of the

ligand (i.e. the substance we are interested in) to the receptor (e.g. a liver nuclear receptor involved in a hepatotoxicity pathway, or the estrogen receptor in endocrine disruption). This binding energy bears a direct relationship with the (expected) potency of a substance, as it is directly related to the receptor/ligand dissociation constant K_d , (see e.g. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Binding_constant) through

$$K_d = e^{\frac{dG}{RT}}$$

with dG being the delta Gibbs free energy, i.e. the binding energy; R the universal molar gas constant and T the temperature in Kelvin. We cannot directly derive an absolute potency from these values of the dissociation constant, but we can use this relationship to establish *relative* potencies, as a substance that is binding 10 times better to the receptor (i.e. has a K_d ten times lower), is also expected to be 10 times more potent. We ignore in this assumption the (finite, and variable) concentration of receptors in different tissues, i.e. we assume low concentrations of the ligand with respect to the receptors for all different types of cells.

Assuming that:

- Same ligand/receptor binding leads to same (adverse) effect (NOAEL); and
- correcting for molar concentration,

we can calculate Relative Binding Factors (RBFs):

$$\text{RBF} = \frac{K_d(\text{ref})}{K_d(\text{unknown})} = e^{\frac{dG(\text{ref})}{RT} - \frac{dG(\text{unknown})}{RT}}$$

With the NOAELs expressed in mmol/kg bw/day, and using a temperature of 307 Kelvin (37°C) as the average body temperature at which the receptor binding takes place, and the ideal molar gas constant of $1.987 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kcal K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ the relative potency becomes 5.15 for each kcal/mol difference in binding energy, or noted differently

$$\text{RBF} = 5.15^{[(dG(\text{ref})-dG(\text{unknown}))]}$$

These RBFs, as calculated for the whole EuroMix Inventory, can be used for several purposes, such as prioritizing of chemicals, selection of chemicals and as a first estimate of actual RPFs for use in mixture risk assessment calculations.

If we now have two substances which exert their toxicological effect through the binding of the same (nuclear) receptor in the organism, of which one (reference) substance has a known potency (e.g. NOAEL

from *in-vivo* experiments), we can calculate the relative potency of the second by comparing the binding energies from the molecular docking experiments as follows:

$$\text{NOAEL(unknown)} = \text{NOAEL(reference)} * \text{RBF}$$

These RBF-corrected NOAELS are expressed as mmol/kg bw/day. To calculate the relative potency factor in terms of NOAELs expressed in mg/kg bw/day one also has to correct for differences in molecular weight by multiplying with the ratio of the Molecular Weight of the two substances. This leads to:

$$\text{NOAEL(unknown)} = \text{NOAEL(reference)} * [\text{MW(unknown)/MW(reference)}] * \text{RBF}$$

Instead of expressing the RBF relative to a (toxicologically) well characterized reference substance, it might be more instructive for ranking and prioritization purposes to express the RBF relative to the threshold of the binding energy threshold that is has also been chosen to distinguish between receptor activity and non-activity, i.e. the value of -6.5 kcal/mol. The equation for expressing the Relative Binding Factor then becomes:

$$\text{RBF(prioritization)} = 5.15^{[-6.5 - dG(\text{unknown})]}$$

If these RBFs are going to be applied in mixture risk assessment, as a first approximation to RPFs, the RBF(prioritization) needs to be expressed as a ratio of RBF(prio) relative to the RBF(prio) of a the reference substance. Thus:

$$\text{RBF} = \frac{\text{RBF(prioritization.unknown)}}{\text{RBF(prioritization.reference)}}$$

Furthermore, when these RBFs are compared to RPFs (as calculation based on the ratio of the NOAELs) one has to take into account the extrapolation from cell internal concentrations (for the RBFs) to external (RPFs based on NOAELs). If the two substances (the reference compound and the unknown compound) have the same kinetics, leading to an identical In Vivo to In Vitro Extrapolation factor (IVIVE factor) the RBF(corrected for molecular weight differences) and the RPF will be equal. Estimation of the IVIVE factor is discussed in section 6, Generic approaches to PBPK modelling of the EuroMix Inventory.

4.4 In vivo read-across from EuroMix Toxicity database (chemical similarity)

This part in the workflow has only superficially been worked out in EuroMix, as there are numerous more advanced ways to perform (case by case, but also automated) read across. As examples we mention the

options of category formation and read across built in the OECD QSAR Toolbox software [OECD, 2017], and software like ToxRead (www.toxread.eu), VEGA (www.vega-qsar.eu) and AMBIT (http://cefic-lri.org/lri_toolbox/ambit/). The concept of selecting those substances that are chemically most similar to a known substance or component of a mixture can be simply illustrated by the use of a Chemical Similarity coefficient, using the most applied algorithm for chemical similarity, i.e. the well known Tanimoto coefficient [Bajusz et al. 2015]. This coefficient ranges from 0 for complete dissimilarity to 1 for completely similar substances. The absolute value of the Tanimoto coefficient () of the most similar substance for which (reliable) *in-vivo* data is available can therefore also serve as an estimate of the probability and/or reliability of the specific read-across for retain and refine purposes.

The similarity of each substance in the EuroMix inventory is calculated with respect to all other entries in the EuroMix inventory. Effectively, this yields a matrix of similarity coefficients of all individual substances in the EuroMix Inventory relative to all other Inventory entries. This is a 1598 x 1598 matrix of similarity coefficients, which can be sorted to give the most similar substances to any of the EuroMix substances. This matrix of similarity coefficients can be integrated in the EuroMix software tool, coupled to the EuroMix Toxicity database in order to allow a user to select the most similar (according to Tanimoto coefficient) substance from the EuroMix Toxicity database, and use the *in-vivo* toxicity test result in a read across, to establish an estimate of the Relative Potency Factor for a substance for which no *in-vivo* data is available. For an example of such a similarity matrix see the 4x4 example on the next page. The Accelrys Accord for Excel add-in software has been used to generate chemical structure fingerprints and the Tanimoto coefficients for the EuroMix inventory. Using different software might give slightly different absolute values of the Tanimoto coefficients (because a different chemical fingerprint is applied), but will overall give highly similar rankings.

If a substance is not present in the EuroMix Inventory, a similarity coefficient of this new substance with respect to the 1598 substances in the EuroMix inventory should be provided by the user. Alternatively the user should be able to provide a case-by-case read-across estimate for the RPF (with the read across performed outside the EuroMix Software tool, with i.e. the previously mentioned tools) and use that in the *in-silico* tier of the mixture risk assessment.

As an illustration of the similarity concept, a 4 x 4 matrix for 4 randomly chosen substances in the EuroMix inventory is given. If we assume that one of these substances does not have a reliable NOAEL on which an RPF can be based (but the others do have a reliable NOAEL), the Tanimoto similarity coefficients given for that substance would determine which of the other 3 substance is considered the most similar substance that would be proposed for read across of the NOAEL, to determine a Relative Potency Factor.

	b-Myrcene Similarity	DEP Similarity	Mecoprop Similarity	MCPA Similarity
 123-35-3 b-Myrcene	1	0.032	0.056	0.044
 84-66-2 Diethyl phthalate	0.032	1	0.296	0.311
 93-65-2 Mecoprop	0.056	0.296	1	0.931
 MCPA 94-74-6	0.044	0.311	0.931	1

In this hypothetical read-across matrix, if the substance of interest, for which we do not have (reliable) *in-vivo* data is MCPA, the most adequate read across structure would be Mecoprop, with a Tanimoto similarity coefficient of 93.1%. The other two substances, DEP with 31.1% similarity and b-Myrcene with only 4.4% similarity, would not be considered structurally close enough to warrant a read across. The structural difference between Mecoprop and MCPA is one methyl-substituent next to the ketone-oxygen. Due to their structural similarity it seems likely that they would bind to the same ligand and trigger a similar Mode of Action. For read across, the hypothesis is that the (structural) similarity is high enough to assume similar potency as well. If mechanistic information is available that would discredit the read-across hypothesis based only on chemical structure similarity, a user should disregard this statistical proposal for read across candidates and apply his or her knowledge of the toxicological endpoint of interest to select the most appropriate read-across candidate from the toxicity database.

So what determines whether the similarity is 'good enough' for read-across?. Therefore, a threshold value for the Tanimoto coefficient is proposed to be applied. The default of this cut-off value is chosen high (0.80, or 80% similarity, a value often used in literature as a cut-off for structural similarity), but a user should be able to override this threshold, and select a "less structurally similar" substance for read-across if this is desired, or deemed (toxicologically, biologically) more plausible. If multiple read across candidates are available that score above the threshold value, it would be ideal if a trend in the potency with increasing or decreasing similarity could be detected. In that case, the closest structural analogue is used for a direct read across of the RPF. If no trend is present, then a worst case approach, reading across from the most potent of the structural analogues, is proposed as the default. In the prioritization exercise for craniofacial malformations (section 5.2) the class of triazoles is an example showing that analogues with a value less than the threshold of 80% can still be meaningful candidates for read-across.

4.5 In vivo data

If a substance is present in the EuroMix Toxicity Database with a NOAEL or LOAEL for the endpoint of interest (i.e. steatosis) then that value can be used for determining the RPF. In case there are multiple NOAELs/LOAELs at first the lowest NOAEL/LOAEL is used, until in depth evaluation of the endpoint would lead to choosing one specific NOAEL/LOAEL or using the (geometric) mean of the NOAELs/LOAELs, or ideally a Benchmark Dose derived from the dose response data. The structural similarity matrix (section 4.4) can be used to determine those substances in the EuroMix inventory that have full similarity, i.e. a Tanimoto coefficient of 1. As there are duplicates in the Toxicity database and in the EuroMix Inventory, sometimes one will be able to find *in-vivo* data for a completely similar substance that is stored under a different name and/or identification number in the database.

5. Prioritization of the EuroMix inventory using the *in-silico* tools

Using the QSAR predictions to distinguish highly probable hepatotoxic from non-hepatotoxic substances, and using the molecular docking derived binding energies to predict MoAs as well as given an indication on the potency (Relative Binding Potency) of all substances in the EuroMix Inventory, we have performed prioritization exercises, using different prioritization criteria to select substances of interest for further testing in the EuroMix battery of *in vitro* assays, developed in Work Package 3 of EuroMix.

5.1 Hepatotoxicity/Steatosis

The 9 different QSAR models for hepatotoxicity of which 4 give specific indications of the phenotype steatosis (described in EuroMix D2.2, and section 3.2 of this report), and 16 liver nuclear receptor docking models that are relevant as MIEs in the EuroMix AOP for steatosis (described in section 3.3), were applied

to the whole EuroMix inventory of 1600 substances. Different selection criteria were applied to the results to propose substances for further (*in-vitro*) testing:

- High potency substances;
- Specific NR MoA triggering substances;
- Steatotic substances triggering multiple (all) Nuclear Receptor MoAs;
- Substances predicted not triggering any Nuclear Receptor MoA , but predicted as steatotic
- Substances predicted not triggering any Nuclear Receptor MoA and predicted not hepatotoxic.

High potency substances.

Using the docking calculations, we can calculate RBFs for the 16 liver nuclear receptors that are involved in the EuroMix AOP steatosis. Within the EuroMix inventory we can then select the most potent liver nuclear receptor binders (any nuclear receptor). This can be done absolute, and or for the different classes of food/feed substances. In this case we calculated RBFs using Flusilazole as the reference compound (Flusilazole RBF=1). The use of RBFs relative not to Flusilazole but to the threshold binding energy of -6.5 kcal/mol (described in section 4.3) would yeald different absolute values of the RBF, but identical order/ranking. In the tables with the top ranking substances also the fraction of the QSAR models that predict a substance to be hepatotoxic is given, as QSARhep+ value. A substance that binds (strongly) to a receptor potentially inducing steatosis in the liver, but which is not predicted by the consensus approach using the hepatotoxicity QSARs, is (much) less likely to actually cause steatosis *in vivo*.

Top 5 Most potent receptor binders (any receptor):

26658-19-5	Sorbitan tristearate	E492	Food Additive	RBF= 940000 (PPARc) QSARhep+ .5
8002-43-5	Lecithins	E322	Food Additive	RBF= 675000 (PPARc) QSARhep+ .63
9005-67-8	Polysorbate 60	E435	Food Additive	RBF= 79000 (PXR) QSARhep+ .5
116355-83-0	Fumonisin B1		Mycotoxins	RBF= 34500 (PPARc) QSARhep+ .4
7173-51-5	Didecyldimethylammoniumchl. PPP fungicide			RBF= 230000 (RARc) QSARhep- .22

For the lecithins entry, the specific results of the calculations for dioleoyl lecithin CAS 4235-95-4 have been used. Didecyldimethylammonium scores high for RARg (and RXRb) receptor binding, but is not predicted to be hepatotoxic by the QSARs. Also fumonisin B1 is not predicted to be hepatotoxic (4/10 QSARs are positive). This can be considered somewhat borderline, so fumonisin could still be an interesting candidate for testing, especially as it triggers PPARg quite potently, but also PXR with an almost similar potency.

Specific NR MoA triggering substances (only 1 MoA, no other modes triggered):

ONLY MoA 1: PPARa antaagonism leading to beta-oxidation inhibition

Although currently the molecular docking calculations cannot be used to distinguish antagonism from agonism, for the prioritization the gross assumption has been used that if a substance *binds* sufficiently to the PPAR α receptor, we *assume* that its effect will be antagonistic (since PPAR α antagonism rather than agonism is associated with steatosis). This leads to a gross over-estimation of the antagonistic potency (the RBF), as a number of the potential PPAR α binders will do so in an agonistic way, not leading to steatosis. Nevertheless, this is a worst case assumption, and can be used effectively for prioritization purposes. Further testing (*in vitro*) should elucidate whether a substance truly has antagonistic properties.

61213-25-0	Flurochloridone	PPP herbicide	RBF= 0.87 (PPAR α)	QSARhep+ .7
210880-92-5	Clothianidin	PPP insecticide	RBF= 0.75 (PPAR α)	QSARhep+ .5

Clothianidin has already been tested in EuroMix WP3. It should be noted that the calculations indicate that the RBF is not very high, and RXR β and RXR γ are also triggered. The same is true for flurochloridone, which seems to trigger also RAR α , RAR β and RXR β and RXR γ according to the calculations.

As a substance that is predicted to have the same MoA as clothianidin, flurochloridone is predicted to be slightly more potent. Both are predicted to be hepatotoxic, but flurochloridone has more positive QSAR predictions in the consensus model (7 instead of 5 for clothianidin).

ONLY MoA 2 fatty acid synthesis stimulation (LXR, PXR, PPAR α , FXR, GR, CAR)

81777-89-1	Clomazone	herbicide	RBF=0.14 (CAR)	QSARhep- .40
944-22-9	Fonofos	insecticides	RBF=0.14 (CAR)	QSARhep- .38
205-82-3	Benzo[j]fluoranthene	env.cont.	RBF=0.30 (FXR)	QSARhep+ .89
62571-86-2	Captopril	pharma	RBF=0.37 (FXR)	QSARhep+ .60
396-01-0	Triamterene	pharma	RBF=0.35 (FXR)	QSARhep+ .60
83-05-6	Bis(4-chlorophenyl)acetic acid	pharma	RBF=0.22 (FXR)	QSARhep+ .70
Various	biphenyls; hex-, to octachloro	env.cont.	RBF=0.56 (PPAR α , LXR)	QSARhep+ .78

The table presents the outcome of molecular docking analysis. The substances that trigger *only* MoA2 do not seem to do so very potent, and most of these also trigger RXR type enzymes. The two substances that trigger CAR are not predicted as causing hepatotoxicity by the QSARs (although the value of .40 indicates that 4 out of 10 QSARs are still predicting positive).

Only MoA 3 Fatty acid influx (LXR, PXR, PPAR α , AhR)

This mode of action has a lot of overlap with the MoA2 (LXR, PXR PPAR γ) and therefore activation of the AhR receptor is what should be setting the MoA3 apart from MoA2. For one food additive and 10 pesticides AhR seems to play a crucial role according to the molecular docking results:

101-21-3	Chlorpropham	growth reg.	RBF=825 (AhR)	QSARhep+ 0.7
3060-89-7	Metobromuron	herbicide	RBF=423 (AhR)	QSARhep+ 0.7
10605-21-7	Carbendazim	fungicide	RBF=423 (AhR)	QSARhep+ 0.7
709-98-8	Propanil	herbicide	RBF=423 (AhR)	QSARhep+ 0.7
21564-17-0	2-(Thiocyanomethylthio)benzothiazole		RBF=423 (AhR)	QSARhep+ .67
330-54-1	Diuron	herbicide	RBF=598 (AhR)	QSARhep+ 0.6
2164-17-2	Fluometuron	herbicide	RBF=845 (AhR)	QSARhep+ 0.6
15545-48-9	Chlorotoluron	herbicide	RBF=1004 (AhR)	QSARhep+ 0.6
121-79-9	Propyl gallate E310	Food additive	RBF=779 (AhR)	QSARhep+ 0.5
2631-40-5	Isoprocarb	insecticide	RBF=485 (AhR)	QSARhep- 0.4
7003-89-6	Chlormequat	growth reg.	RBF=425400 (AhR)	QSARhep- 0.1

Two of the PPPs are not predicted to be hepatotoxic, and are therefore less good candidates. The food additive propyl gallate can be expected to have exposures, therefore seems a good candidate for further testing.

Only MoA 4 RAR activation leading to direct triglyceride accumulation

This mode of action is not very precisely defined (in terms of the mode of action on the cellular level) and it should be noted that a lot of the substances that trigger the PPAR, PXR or LXR receptors are also predicted as potentially active for the RXR receptor, and therefore might be involved in RAR as well. For the selection we looked specifically at the RAR α , β , γ binding energies, not RXR.

Only two substances (one PPP and one food additive) seem to be exclusively binding to RAR:

1214-39-7	6-Benzyladenine	growth reg.	RBF 1.3 (RAR γ)	QSARhep+ 0.6
100-97-0	Hexamethylene tetramine E239	Food additive	RBF=35 (RAR α)	QSARhep- 0.3

The food additive hexamethylene tetramine is not predicted by the QSARs to be hepatotoxic, and therefore is a less interesting candidate for further testing from the toxicity point of view, but might be interesting from an exposure point of view. The binding potency for 6-benzyladenine is only 1.3 times the potency of flusilazole, and the binding potency of hexamethylene tetramine is 35 times the potency of flusilazole. This seems to be contradicting the QSAR prediction of hepatotoxicity but is not necessarily wrong.

Steatotic Substances triggering multiple (all) Nuclear Receptor MoAs

Substances that are predicted to bind significantly to at least one NR in at least one of the 4 NR mediated MoA for steatosis, and are predicted to be hepatotoxic by QSAR, with at least one steatosis QSAR also predicting positive would all be candidate for further testing. However, the number of substances fulfilling these requirements in the Inventory is 725 (of 1600). We already selected candidates that exclusively trigger one NR MoA, here we select the substances that predicted with the highest probability to cause steatosis via any (or preferably) all NR MoA. The rationale is that all NR MoA seem to be dose additive anyway, based on the first rounds of measurements with the in vitro assays in EuroMix.

For two substances all QSAR models (10/10) predict that they are hepatotoxic and steatotic. Both trigger NRs in all 4 NR related MoA for steatosis, both are predicted to bind significantly to the AhR receptor. These two substances are:

188425-85-6	boscalid	fungicide	#NR=12/16	RBF=10.9 (RXRc)
149877-41-8	Bifenazate	acaricide	#NR=15/16	RBF=9.4 (RARc)

The number of NRs that are bound above the threshold value (and are therefore predicted to be activated) is given as #NR. Also the highest Relative Binding Factor is given, with the NR related to that binding factor (relative to Flusilazole).

Another 20 substances are predicted with still a very probability (9/10 or 8/9 QSARs positive) to be hepatotoxic. Out of these 22 substances 15 do trigger all 4 steatosis AoP NR MoAs simultaneously. The substances are given with the two receptors that show the highest Relative Binding Factor (compared to Flusilazole), and in bold the 5 substances that would also be selected due to their predicted PXR binding (see last section in this document):

72490-01-8	Fenoxycarb	PPP	insecticide	RBF=212 (AhR), 12 (RARa)
28772-56-7	Bromadiolone	PPP	rodenticides	RBF=108 (FXR), 90 (PXR)
139968-49-3	Metaflumizone	PPP	insecticide	RBF= 58 (PPARb), 54 (LXRb)
119446-68-3	Difenoconazole	PPP	fungicide	RBF= 43 (RARa), 15 (LXRa)
55179-31-2	Bitertanol	PPP	fungicide	RBF= 28 (RARc), 15 (RARb)
131807-57-3	Famoxadone	PPP	fungicide	RBF= 17 (PXR), 12 (LXRa)
183675-82-3	Penthiopyrad	PPP	fungicide	RBF= 11 (PPARa), 9 (RARc)
142891-20-1	Cinidon ethyl	PPP	herbicide	RBF= 11 (PPARa), 10 (RARc)
50892-23-4	Wy 14643		pharmaceutical	RBF= 11 (PPARg), 2.9 (PPARa)
6795-23-9	Aflatoxin M1		mycotoxin	RBF= 6.7 (AhR), 1.4 (RARb)
1162-65-8	Aflatoxin B1		mycotoxin	RBF= 4 (AhR), 1.3 (PPARa)
56-53-1	diethylstilbestrol (DES)		pharmaceutical	RBF= 2.7 (PPARg), 0.9 (RARc)
7220-81-7	Aflatoxin B2		mycotoxin	RBF= 2.2 (RARc), 1.6 (PPARa)

1165-39-5	Aflatoxin G1	mycotoxin	RBF= 1.9 (PPARa), 1.5 (RARb)
84-17-3	Dienestrol	pharmaceutical	RBF= 1 (PPARa), 1 (PPARc)

Two substances are predicted as hepatotoxic/steatotic with high probability and calculated by Molecular Docking to only bind sufficiently to trigger MoA2 and 3:

76674-21-0	Flutriafol	PPP	fungicide	RBF= 4.7 (AhR), 0.8 (PXR)
193-39-5	Indeno[1,2,3-cd]pyrene	env.poll.		RBF= 0.6 (RARa), 0.5 (PPARg)

Another environmental pollutant (a PAH) is predicted with high probability to cause hepatotoxicity, and Molecular Docking indicates that only MoA2 (fatty acid synthesis stimulation by LXR, PXR, PPARg, FXR, GR, CAR activation) is involved:

205-82-3	Benzo[j]fluoranthene	env.poll.	RBF= 0.6 (PPARa), 0.4 (LXRa)
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Three substances are calculated to only binding significantly to the RXR receptors, and therefore officially do not qualify as triggering any of the 4 defined MoA, but could be hypothesized to act equal to MoA 4, RAR-mediated steatosis mechanism of action.

86-87-3	1-Naphthylacetic acid (1-NAA)	plant growth regulator	RXRb and RXRc
205-99-2	Benzo[b]fluoranthene	env.poll.	RXRb
207-08-9	Benzo[k]fluoranthene	env.poll.	RXRb

Substances predicted not triggering any Nuclear Receptor MoA , but predicted as steatotic

The number of substances that do not trigger any of the Nuclear Receptors that were modeled by Molecular Docking, but are predicted to be hepatotoxic (by the battery of hepatotoxicity QSARs) is quite high, 157 substances in the total inventory of 1600 substances. If we also filter on the substances that trigger at least one of the 4 steatosis related QSAR models this only reduces by two compounds, i.e. 155 substances are predicted to be steatotic, but do not bind above the minimal receptor binding energy required to classify a substance to any of the Nuclear Receptor mode of actions defined in the EuroMix Steatosis AOP.

For further testing we focus on the substances that are predicted to be steatotic with the highest probability, i.e. 9 or out of 10 (or in one instance 8 out of 9) QSAR models for hepatotoxicity are positive. This gives us 7 candidates (one PPP/Biocide, 3 environmental contaminants and 3 other substances) for further testing:

148-79-8	Thiabendazole	PPP/Biocide	RBF	QSARhep+ 0.9
34883-41-5	3,5-Dichlorobiphenyl	Env poll	RBF	QSARhep+ 0.9

206-44-0	Fluoranthene	Env poll	RBF	QSARhep+ 0.9
205-12-9	7H-Benzo[c]fluorine	Env poll	RBF	QSARhep+ 0.9
131-56-6	2,4-dihydroxybenzophenone	other	RBF	QSARhep+ 0.9
611-99-4	4,4'-Dihydroxybenzophenone	other	RBF	QSARhep+ 0.9
92-88-6	4,4'-Biphenol	other	RBF	QSARhep+ 0.9

Substances predicted not triggering any Nuclear Receptor MoA and predicted not hepatotoxic.

The number of substances that do not bind to steatosis related Nuclear receptors (as determined by molecular docking analysis), and are not predicted to be not hepatotoxic is 155. Those that are predicted to be not hepatotoxic with the highest probability, i.e. only 1 out of 10 (or 1 out of 9) models predict a substance to be hepatotoxic is 20. There are no substances that are predicted not hepatotoxic by any model. (0 out of 10 models). The number of unique substances reduces from 20 to 12 if we group the citrates, tartrates and mannitol. The majority of the predicted non-hepatotoxic substances are food additives.

The 20 non-hepatotoxic substances in the inventory predicted to be negative for hepatotoxicity with a high probability (9 out of 10 QSAR models predict no hepatotoxicity) are:

115-77-5	2,2-Bis(Bromomethyl)-1,3 propanediol	Solvent/plasticizer/monomers/intermediate
38260-01-4	Trientine hydrochloride	Pharmaceutical
102-71-6	Triethanolamine	Used in cosmetics and personal care products, lubricants and greases, washing & cleaning products, pH regulators and water treatment products and paper chemicals and dyes.
69-65-8	D-mannitol	
50-70-4	Sorbitol	E420
87-78-5	Mannitol	E421
139-05-9	Cyclamic acid	E952
87-99-0	Xylitol	E967
110-17-8	Fumaric acid	E297
77-92-9	Citric acid	E330
68-04-2	Sodium citrates	E331
866-84-2	Potassium citrates	E332
813-94-5	Calcium citrates	E333
526-83-0	Tartaric acid (L-+))	E334
868-18-8	(anhydrous) Sodium tartrates	E335
921-53-9 (L)	Potassium tartrates	E336
6381-59-5	Sodium potassium tartrate	E337
3164-34-9	(anhydrous) Calcium tartrate	E354
110-15-6	Succinic acid	E363
3458-72-8	Triammonium citrate	E380

Substances that should be very potent PXR binders (and are predicted to be steatotic/hepatotoxic)

If we look at the high probability substances for steatosis/hepatotoxicity (all, 9/10 or 8/9 QSARs positive), the 5 most potent PXR binders have all been mentioned in the previous list of “Steatotic Substances that triggering multiple (all) Nuclear Receptor MoAs”:

28772-56-7	Bromadiolone	rodenticides	PXR RBF=90.9
139968-49-3	Metaflumizone	insecticide	PXR RBF=49.9
131807-57-3	Famoxadone	fungicide	PXR RBF=16.6
119446-68-3	Difenoconazole	fungicide	PXR RBF=13.3
142891-20-1	Cinidon ethyl	herbicide	PXR RBF= 8.1

Their PXR binding affinity can be an extra argument to select these substances for further testing.

If we lower the QSAR prediction probability threshold for hepatotoxicity to 8/10 or 7/9 QSARs we find several other potent PXR binders, that were not identified in previous lists:

111479-05-1	Propaquizafop	herbicide	PXR RBF= 128
119738-06-6	Quizalofop-P-tefuryl	herbicide	PXR RBF= 108
85536-03-4	chlorophyllins E140	Food additive	PXR RBF= 75
134605-64-4	Butafenacil	herbicide	PXR RBF= 74
80844-07-1	Etofenprox	insecticide	PXR RBF= 51
NO CAS_	Pfizer7	pharmaceutical	PXR RBF= 46
82640-04-8	Raloxifene hydrochloride	pharmaceutical	PXR RBF= 41

Such a selection of specific Nuclear Receptor high potency substances can be performed for each receptor, i.e. PPAR α , PPAR γ , LXR, etc. Because the PXR assay seemed to be well predictive of steatosis in the first in vitro testing round, the selection of substances using the calculated Molecular Docking energies focusses on PXR first.

An excel sheet summarizing the results of the prioritization exercise for Hepatotoxicity/steatosis is given in Annex I.

5.2 Developmental toxicity/craniofacial malformations

The relevant QSARs(4 models, VEGA CAESAR, VEGA PG, DEREK, TEST) and calculated receptor binding energies (AhR binding) are applied for prioritization in a similar way as for hepatotoxicity, however, the lack

of specific nuclear receptor binding models for the endpoint of developmental toxicity makes the procedure much more limited.

Substances predicted to be developmental toxic with high probability

From the complete inventory of 1598 substances, only 36 are predicted to be developmental toxic by all 4 QSAR models. From these 11 are plant protection products, but a significant amount of predicted developmental toxicants is coming from other regulatory pillars, with 6 Food Contact materials and 19 pharmaceutical or other uses.

71751-41-2	Abamectin	PPP	acaricide, insecticide, nematicide
67375-30-8	Alpha - Cypermethrin	PPP	insecticide, acaricide
64-82-5	Amitrole (aminotriazole)	PPP	herbicide
144-54-7	metam sodium	PPP	fungicide, herbicide, nematicide
148-79-8	Thiabendazole	PPP	fungicide
36734-19-7	Iprodione	PPP	fungicide
32809-16-8	Procymidone	PPP	fungicide
10605-21-7	Carbendazim	PPP	fungicide
17804-35-2	Benomyl	PPP	acaricide, fungicide, nematicide
128-03-0	Potassium dimethyldithiocarbamate	PPP	herbicide
148-79-8	Thiabendazole	PPP	fungicide
57-56-7	Semicarbazide	NIAS-FCM	
556-52-5	Glycidol	NIAS-FCM	solvents-plasticizers-monomers-
104-76-7	2-Ethyl-1-hexanol	NIAS-FCM	plasticizer
84-66-2	Diethyl phthalate	NIAS-FCM	plasticizer
68-12-2	N,N-Dimethylformamide	NIAS-FCM	solvent
107-12-0	Propionitrile	NIAS-FCM	solvent
51-21-8	5-fluorouracil		pharmaceutical
302-79-4	all-trans retinoic acid		pharmaceutical
56-53-1	diethylstilbestrol (DES)		pharmaceutical
13311-84-7	flutamide		pharmaceutical
84-16-2	hexestrol		pharmaceutical
58-14-0	Pyrimethamine		pharmaceutical
83-67-0	Theobromine		pharmaceutical
99-66-1	valproic acid		pharmaceutical
521-18-6	Dihydrotestosterone		other, pharmaceutical
62571-86-2	Captopril		other
17230-88-5	Danazol		other
302-22-7	Chlormadinone acetate		other
146-56-5	Fluphenazine hydrochloride		other
130-61-0	Thioridazine hydrochloride		other
59-66-5	Acetazolamide		other
59-05-2	Methotrexate		other

54-31-9	Flurosemide	other
491-80-5	Biochanin A	other
50-18-0	Cyclophosphamide	other

Substances predicted to be NOT developmental toxic

229 Substances of the whole inventory of 1598 substances are predicted to be NOT developmental toxic, as none of the 4 models gives a positive result. Interpreting this as a prediction of NON-developmental toxicity is (much) more uncertain than the prediction of developmental toxicity based on all four models being positive. This is a result of the cooper statistics of the four models, showing a high positive predictive value (if the prediction is positive, this has a high probability of being correct) and a relatively high false negative rate (the amount of false negative predictions is high).

Nevertheless the relative occurrence of substances from regulatory pillars does seem to be relevant. From the 229 substances, 64 are food additives, whereas not any food additive is present in the group of substances predicted to be developmental toxic with a high probability (previous section).

Furthermore 127 substances of the 229 are Environmental pollutants, with the bulk coming from different polychlorinated biphenyls together with PAHs and poly- and perfluorinated substances. Again, no environmental pollutants from the EuroMix Inventory were on the list of 36 predicted developmental toxicants with a high probability.

The table of substances predicted to be not developmental toxic is given in Annex II, together with the rest of the results of the prioritization exercise for Developmental toxicity/Craniofacial malformations.

Substances with predicted high potency for binding to AhR

The only Nuclear receptor in the AOP for developmental toxicity / cranial malformations is the AhR receptor. The top 5 substances binding to the AhR receptor are:

				AhR RBF (flusilazole = 1)
7003-89-6	Chlormequat	PPP	plant growth regulator	RBF=425415
999-81-5	chlormequat – chloride	PPP	plant growth regulator	RBF=425415
76902-90-4	Methenammonium chloride	PPP	Microbiocide	RBF=106760
8001-54-5	Benzalkonium chloride (BAC)	PPP	algicide, fungicide	RBF=62600
7173-51-5	Didecyldimethylammonium chloride	PPP	Fungicide	RBF=5656

From these five only the microbiocide methan ammonium chloride (CAS 76902-90-4) is predicted by 2 out of 4 of the developmental QSAR models to be a developmental toxicant. The substance is used as a preservative / antibactericide among others in cosmetics. The other four substances are predicted to be a developmental toxicant by only one model (TEST for Chlormequat and chlormequat-chloride, and VEGA-CAESAR for Benzalkonium chloride and didcyldimethylammonium chloride).

Non-PPP substances in the EuroMix Inventory that have relative binding potencies to AhR of 100 or more when compared to flusilazole are:

				AhR	
				RBF	QSARs+
102-76-1	Glyceryl triacetate; triacetin	Food Additive	E1518, other	994	1/4
121-79-9	Propyl gallate	Additive	E310, Antioxidants	779	2/4
153719-23-4	thiamethoxam	Biocide		598	2/4
138261-41-3	Imidacloprid	Biocide		503	1/4
15625-89-5	Trimethylolpropanetriacrylate	NIAS-FCM	solvents-plasticizers-	423	1/4
210880-92-5	clothianidin	Biocide		300	2/4
	4-Hexylresorcinol	ADD	E586, Antioxidants	266	1/4
131-18-0	di-n-pentyl phthalate (DPP)	NIAS-FCM	Plasticizer in FCM	252	2/4
120-47-8	Ethyl p-hydroxybenzoate	Food Additive	E214	198	2/4
64519-82-0	Isomalt	Food Additive	E953	180	2/4
25395-31-7	Glyceryl diacetate (diacetin)	Food Additive	E1517	130	2/4
84-66-2	Diethyl phthalate	NIAS-FCM	plasticizer	126	2/4
22839-47-0	Aspartame	Food Additive	E951	110	1/4
112-27-6	Triethylene glycol	NIAS-FCM	plasticizer	106	1/4

Chemical similarity with substances known to cause Craniofacial Malformations

As molecular docking results for specific receptors related to craniofacial malformations are not available, other methods have to be used to select substances that are likely to have similar properties in binding to those receptors and potentially cause the same type of effects, through disruption of the same Adverse Outcome Pathway. One simple method is chemical similarity, as described as an option to select appropriate substances for read-across when estimating a Relative Potency Factor for mixture components for which no *in vivo* data is available – Section 4.4 of this Deliverable. This approach works to select candidates for known or hypothesized AOPs, but would be the only option if no AOP / receptor binding pathway is known or available.

- **Triazoles**

Triazoles are supposed to disturb the Retinoic Acid pathway, and thereby causing developmental toxicity, by inhibiting CYP26. The targeted function of the triazole fungicides, making them effective against fungi, is to inhibit CYP51. There are 41 structures containing the triazole ring in the EuroMix Inventory:

- | | | |
|---|---------------------|---------------------------------|
| 1. Amitrole
(aminotriazole) | 15. Tetraconazole | 30. Metosulam |
| 2. Flusilazole | 16. Triticonazole | 31. Pyroxsulam |
| 3. Tebuconazole | 17. Triadimenol | 32. Penoxsulam |
| 4. Penconazole | 18. Diniconazole | 33. Azafenidin |
| 5. Flutriafol | 19. Triadimefon | 34. Sulfentrazone |
| 6. Ipconazole | 20. Ametoctradin | 35. Flucarbazone-sodium |
| 7. Metconazole | 21. propiconazole | 36. Carfentrazone-ethyl |
| 8. Paclobutrazol | 22. propiconazole | 37. Thiencarbazone |
| 9. Myclobutanil | 23. Epoxiconazole | 38. Propoxycarbazone-
sodium |
| 10. Fenbuconazole | 24. Difenconazole | 39. Thiencarbazone -
Methyl |
| 11. Triazophos | 25. Triazolam | |
| 12. Cyproconazole | 26. Bromuconazole | |
| 13. Bitertanol | 27. Fluquinconazole | |
| 14. Hexaconazole | 28. Florasulam | |
| 29. Amisulbrom | | |
| 40. 1H-1,2,4-Triazole-1-ethanol, a-(1-chlorocyclopropyl)-a-[(2-chlorophenyl)methyl]- | | |
| 41. 1H-1,2,4-Triazole-3-carboxylic acid, 1-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-5-(trichloromethyl)-, ethyl ester | | |

The triazole compound tested at RIVM with the highest potency (in the zebrafish embryo assay) is Triadimefon. EuroMix Inventory substances that are most similar to Triadimefon are:

				Tanimoto coeff.	#QSAR+
55219-65-3	Triadimenol	PPP	fungicide	0.83	2/4
55179-31-2	Bitertanol	PPP	fungicide	0.76	2/4
107534-96-3	Tebuconazole	PPP		0.51	2/4
76738-62-0	Paclobutrazol	PPP	plant growth regulator	0.50	2/4

It is remarkable that Triadimenol, the most similar substance to Triadimefon in the Inventory, only scores a similarity coefficient of 0.83. Triadimenol is an (active) metabolite of Triadimefon. This illustrates that the absolute value of the similarity coefficient is not a very good measure of the “goodness” of a possible read across candidate.

- **TCDD**

2,3,7,8-tetrachloro-dibenzo-p-dioxine (TCDD) is thought to lead to developmental malformation by disturbing the AhR receptor. This adverse outcome pathway is represented by the selection of substances with high (relative) potency to the AhR receptor (see previous section). Two substances that are considered as scaffold substances triggering this pathway are the environmental contaminants TCDD and the Dioxin-

like polychlorinated biphenyl PCB-126 (3,3',4,4',5-pentachlorobiphenyl). TCDD similarity gives the following EuroMix inventory candidates:

			Tanimoto coeff.	AhR RBF	#QSAR+
1746-01-6	2,3,7,8-Tetrachlorodibenzo-p-dioxin (TCDD)	Env.Cont.	1	0.063	2/4
No CAS	1,2,3,7,8,9-HxCDD	Env.Cont.	0.885	0.051	3/4
57653-85-7	1,2,3,6,7,8-HxCDD	Env.Cont.	0.885	0.0038	3/4
40321-76-4	1,2,3,7,8-PeCDD	Env.Cont.	0.885	0.1349	3/4
3268-87-9	OCDD	Env.Cont.	0.868	0.0000	2/4
82291-36-9	1,2,4,6,9-PCDD	Env.Cont.	0.868	0.0035	3/4
35822-46-9	1,2,3,4,6,7,8-HpCDD	Env.Cont.	0.868	0.0056	2/4
39227-28-6	1,2,3,4,7,8-HxCDD	Env.Cont.	0.868	0.0124	3/4

The next best candidate was pentachlorophenol with a similarity of 0.55

Although the similarity is almost equal between the tetra, penta, hexa and hepta-chlorodibenzo-p-dioxins, it is interesting to see the difference in relative AhR binding. This indicates that the penta chloro substance 1,2,3,7,8-PeCDD, would be the most potent candidate, possibly even more potent than TCDD itself. Both TCDD and this penta chloro compound are attributed a WHO Toxic Equivalence factor (WHO-TEF) of 1. This nicely confirms the chemical similarity approach.

PCB-126 (3,3',4,4',5-pentachlorobiphenyl; TEF=0.1) gives a large number of potentially structural very similar candidates for further testing, as a large number of PCB's have been included in the Inventory. Seven PCB's in the inventory have (despite a different chlorination pattern) even similarity coefficient of 1 with PCB-126:

			Tanimoto coeff.	AhR RBF	#QSAR+
32774-16-6	3,3',4,4',5,5'-Hexachlorobiphenyl, PCB169, TEF=0.03		1	.002	2/4
70362-50-4	3,4,4',5-Tetrachlorobiphenyl, PCB81, TEF=0.0003		1	.063	1/4
57465-28-8	3,3',4,4',5-Pentachlorobiphenyl, PCB126, TEF=0.1		1	.013	2/4
39635-33-1	3,3',4,5,5'-Pentachlorobiphenyl		1	.008	2/4
41464-48-6	3,3',4,5'-Tetrachlorobiphenyl		1	.032	1/4
70362-49-1	3,3',4,5-Tetrachlorobiphenyl		1	.032	1/4
53555-66-1	3,4,5-Trichlorobiphenyl		1	.027	1/4

These seven PCB compounds also (all) have a similarity coefficient of 0.25 with TCDD. Based on the Relative Binding Potency (relative to Flusilazole) the dioxins and PCB's can not be considered very potent AhR

binders/activators. However, for these compounds the toxicokinetics – their persistence, i.e. long residence time in the body, and their bioaccumulating behaviour – will lead to relatively high internal concentrations for a given (continuous) external exposure, which might contribute significantly to their in vivo potency.

- Valproic acid

Valproic acid is considered as an example of a highly potent HDAC inhibitor. Substances that are highly similar to valproic acid in the EuroMix Chemical Inventory are:

				Tanimoto coeff.	#QSAR+
99-66-1	valproic acid	pharmaceutical		1	4/4
149-57-5	2-Ethylhexanoic acid	NIAS-FCM		0.909	3/4
124-04-9	Adipic acid	food additive	E355	0.818	1/4
107-92-6	butyric acid	food additive		0.75	0/4
104-76-7	2-Ethyl-1-hexanol	NIAS-FCM	plasticizer	0.667	1/4

The most similar substance, 2-ethylhexanoic acid, seems a particularly good candidate for testing valproic acid type of developmental toxicity. The next two substances, having slightly lower similarity to valproic acid, are predicted by only 1 or no QSAR model to be developmental toxic. The short(er) carbon chain length when compared to valproic acid probably makes these substances much less potent. The last candidate, 2-ethyl-1-hexanol, scores lower on the similarity, and is also only predicted by only 1 QSAR model to be developmental toxic, but metabolic considerations would indicate that this substance is a precursor of 2-ethylhexanoic acid, and therefore might be an interesting candidate, together with the 2-ethylhexanoic acid, for further testing. This result shows that chemical similarity, as well as the knowledge in the QSAR models, does not cover the metabolic pathways that might lead to transformation/activation of substances. This is something to be particularly aware of. The uses of 2-ethylhexanoic acid are: PVC stabilizers, Plasticizers, Coating driers, Synthetic lubricants, Pharmaceuticals, Catalysts, Other chemical intermediate uses.

- Retinoic Acid

The retinoic acid pathway should involve interaction with the RAR and RXR receptor, both have been modelled in the EuroMix Molecular docking exercise. Substances with a high structural similarity to Retinoic Acid are:

Tanimoto coeff.	RARc RBF	#QSAR+
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302-79-4	all-trans retinoic acid	pharma	1	40	4/4
1107-26-2	Beta-apo-8'-carotenal (C30)	Food Additive E160e	0.82	132	2/4
	Canthaxanthin	Food Additive E161g	0.72	0	2/4
	Paprika extract; Capsanthin;	Food Additive E160c	0.69	63	2/4
514-78-3	Carotenes	Food Additive E160a	0.67	42	0/4
	Annatto; Bixin; Norbixin	Food Additive E160b	0.67	42	2/4

These are all food additives, used as colouring agent. The first candidate (carotenal) also shows good potency in the Molecular Docking calculations towards RARc (~3 fold the binding energy of retinoic acid), but also for RARa, RARb, RXRa, RXRb and RXRc the binding energies indicate stronger binding than for retinoic acid.

- Dithiocarbamates

The mode of action of dithiocarbamates is not very well understood. Dithiocarbamate substances that show developmental toxicity giving craniofacial malformations are Metam, Thiram and Maneb. Of these three Thiram was experimentally determined to have the highest potency for causing developmental malformations. Substances that are Structurally similar to Thiram are:

			Tanimoto coeff.	#QSAR+
137-26-8	thiram	PPP	1	3/4
97-77-8	disulfiram	PPP	0.78	2/4
128-03-0	Potassium dimethyldithiocarbamate	PPP	0.5	4/4
144-54-7	metam sodium	PPP	0.46	4/4
142-59-6	Ethylenebisdithiocarbamate, disodium	PPP	0.33	1/4
533-74-4	Dazomet	Biocide	0.33	2/4

Based on similarity Disulfiram seems like a good candidate for further testing, despite the similarity which is just below the 0.8 threshold. When looking at the battery of QSARs for developmental toxicity the next similar substance, Potassium dimethyldithiocarbamate (Busan) would be a better candidate as a dithiocarbamate with high potency for developmental malformations.

- Other substances with unknown mechanism

Some other substances showing strong potency in causing craniofacial malformations, but for which no known mode of action can currently be identified, are 2,4-DiNitroPhenol (2,4-DNP), Boric acid and Fenpropimorph. Using these substances for a similarity search in the EuroMix Inventory gives the following lists of most similar substances as possible candidates for further developmental craniofacial malformations testing:

- *2,4-DNP, 2,4-dinitrophenol*

			Tanimoto coeff.	#QSAR+
100-02-7	4-Nitrophenol	PPP	0.82	1/4
824-39-5	Sodium o-nitrophenolate	Plant growth stimulator	0.80	1/4
2581-34-2	3-Methyl-4-nitrophenol	PPP	0.71	1/4
67233-85-6	Sodium 5-nitroguaiacolate	Plant growth stimulator	0.67	2/4

Specifically the mechanism of action of the plant protection product Sodium 5-nitroguaiacolate, and the fact that 2 out of 4 developmental toxicity QSAR models predict this substance to be developmental toxic make this a possibly interesting further testing candidate.

- *Boric acid*

			Tanimoto coeff.	#QSAR+
7440-43-9	cadmium (Cd)	Env.Pollutant	0.14	n.a.
14797-55-8	nitrate	Env.Pollutant	0.14	n.a.
7439-97-6	mercury (Hg)	Env.Pollutant	0.14	n.a.
124-38-9	Carbon dioxide	Food additive E290	0.125	0/4

The very low similarity of the highest scoring substances, and their inorganic nature make these substances very weak analogues, and no good analogue of boric acid as a candidate for further testing can be identified in this way in the EuroMix Inventory.

- *Fenpropimorph*

				Tanimoto coeff.	#QSAR+
67564-91-4	Fenpropimorph	PPP fungicide		0.1	2/4
67306-00-7	Fenpropidin	PPP fungicide		0.69	2/4
147-24-0	Diphenhydramine HCl	Pharma Antihistaminic		0.56	1/4
1593-77-7	Dodemorph	PPP fungicide		0.55	2/4

Fenpropidin, despite the low absolute similarity coefficient of 0.69 is the most structurally similar substances, but lacks the morpholine ring structure present in fenpropimorph. Dodemorph does have the same morpholine functionality, but the substituent to the morpholine ring is quite different as in fenpropimorph. If any indication can be found whether the morpholine ring structure is one of the “structural alerts” related to the developmental toxicity / craniofacial malformations induced by

fenpropmorph, then Dodemorph might be a more sensible analogue. From the shape/steric formation Fenpropidin is the best structural analogue for fenpropimorph in the EuroMix Inventory.

5.3 Endocrine Disruption/estrogen and androgen receptor pathways

No prioritization exercise for estrogen and androgen receptor binding (as Molecular Initiating Event for the endocrine disruption pathway) has been performed. The tools described in this deliverable, and the procedures used in the prioritization for hepatotoxicity and developmental toxicity can be applied in the same manner to the EuroMix Inventory for the endpoint endocrine disruption. As there is no room for extra experimental work in WP3/endocrine, there was at this moment no internal need to generate a list of candidate substances for further testing.

6. Generic PBTK approaches for EuroMix

Incorporation of kinetics to quantitative in vitro to in vivo extrapolations (QIVIVE) is a key step for the realization of a non-animal testing paradigm, in the sphere of regulatory toxicology. The use of Physiologically-Based Toxicokinetic (PBTK) modelling for determining systemic concentrations of chemicals at the target site is accepted to be an indispensable element for such purposes. Nonetheless, PBTK models are usually designed for a single compound or a group of compounds and are considered demanding, with respect to experimental data needed for model parameterization. At RIVM previous experience with generic PBTK modelling has been attained [Fragki et al. 2017], applying available QSAR models to estimate the physico-chemical properties that allow derivation of a PBK model parameterization. This publication focussed on the use of the IndusChemFate model [Jongeneelen and Ten Berge, 2011]. In EuroMix the decision has been made to use COSMOS PBK model for development of specific PBTK models for the ABC chemicals tested in binary and tertiary mixtures for the three endpoints (hepatotoxicity, developmental toxicity and endocrine disruption).

As input the model requires physiological/anatomical parameters (organ volumes, blood flows, cardiac output and alveolar ventilation), biochemical parameters (hepatic Michaelis-Menten kinetics, i.e., maximal metabolic rate (V_{max}), affinity constant for the parent compound and metabolites (K_m) and physicochemical parameters (octanol-water partition coefficient, vapour pressure, molecular weight, water solubility and density). In the model the latter parameters are used for calculating blood concentration: organ partition coefficients and renal clearance.

The parameterization of the COSMOS model is very similar to IndusChemFate, except for Dermal exposure: IndusChem uses a relatively complex model. Currently no dermal exposure module is incorporated in the EuroMix implementation of the COSMOS model in the software tool.

The COSMOS chemical dependent parameterization can be estimated using the relationships in the IndusChemFate model approach; this approach, with the relevant relationships is given in the table on the next page.

In WP7 it was decided that a dermal exposure module would also be added to the COSMOS model implementation in the EuroMix software tool (WP6). When that is realized the approaches for generic, QSAR based, parameterization also of the dermal exposure module as proposed in IndusChemFate model can be followed. The required physico-chemical properties also for the dermal exposure module have already been calculated for the whole EuroMix inventory.

The whole approach to generic PBTK modelling is still being developed in EuroMix, especially the software implementation of the COSMOS model. A more detailed description of the underlying approaches of estimating the COSMOS input parameterization using QSAR models from literature (as described a.o. in the IndusChemFate documentation) will be given in EuroMix Deliverable 7.3: EuroMix PBTK models. PBTK modelling was not a part of the Work Package 2 deliverables, but as QSAR modelling for the generic approach is involved, WP2 is strongly involved in WP7 development of PBTK models. The first results are reported here briefly, but will be documented in detail in D7.3.

Parameters	Symbols	QSAR (as used in IndusChem model)	PhysChem parameter required for input
Molecular Mass	<i>MM</i>	direct calc. from atom masses	-
Blood / air	<i>PCAir</i>	if LHen < -0.7: $0.1933 * (1 / 10 ^ {LHen}) + 0.002592 * 10 ^ {LKoair}$ if LHen >= -0.7 $2.32245 * (1 / 10 ^ {LHen}) + 0.0067389 * 10 ^ {LKoair}$	LHen, LKoair
Fat / blood	<i>PCFat</i>	If LKow < -1 Then LKow = -1 If LKow > 5 Then LKow = 5 $PCFat = 10 ^ {(1.106 * LKow - 0.1253 * LKow ^ 2 - 0.451)}$ If PCFat < 0.05 Then PCFat = 0.05	LKow
Liver / blood	<i>PCLiver</i>	$PCLiver = 10 ^ {(0.15094 * LKow - 0.1111)}$	LKow
Poorly perfused / blood	<i>PCPoor</i>	$PCPoor = PCskin = 10 ^ {(0.05211 * LKow - 0.2239)}$	LKow
Richly perfused / blood	<i>PCRich</i>	$PCRich = 10 ^ {(0.3125 * LKow - 0.1784)}$	LKow
Viable skin / blood	<i>PCSkin</i>	$PCskin / blood = 10 ^ {(0.05211 * LKow - 0.2239)}$	LKow
Viable skin / stratum corneum	<i>PCSkin_sc</i>	$PCSkin_sc = 0.72 * Kow(at\ pH5.4) ^ {0.43}$	Kow(pH5.5)
Unbound fraction in blood	<i>fup</i>	$fup = 0.993 / (0.993 + 0.007 * 10 ^ {LKow})$	LKow

Fraction absorbed by gut	<i>Frac</i>	100%	
Oral absorption rate	<i>kGut</i>	3 /hour	
Renal excretion rate	<i>Ke</i>	NormDist * LKow If Ke > 0.99 Then Ke = 0.99 If Ke < 0.01 Then Ke = 0.01	LKow
Maximum rate of metabolism And MM constant	<i>Vmax</i> <i>Km</i>	Vmax/Km ratio is assumed constant, input = \sim t1/2 (whole body clearance))	t1/2
Skin diffusion coefficient	<i>Kp_sc_vs</i>	$Kp_sc_vs = 3 * (0.043 / MM^{1.361}) + (10^{(-2.59 + 0.7318 * LKow(pH5.4) - 0.006832 * MM)})$	MM LKow(pH5.5)

Calculation of all COSMOS PBK input parameters for the whole EuroMix Inventory has been performed in the meantime. An example of the parameterization for Cypermethrin is given here:

Cypermethrin, EuromixCode PPP-15, CAS RN 52315-07-8

Structure (SMILES): CC1(C(C1C(=O)OC(C#N)c2cccc(c2)Oc3ccccc3)C=C(Cl)Cl)C

Phys-chem input for Parameterization (from Phys/Chem QSARs)

Molecular Mass	416.31	g/mol
Henry Coefficient	7.89E-7	
Log Koctanol/air	11.7	
Log Koctanol/water	6.6	
Log D pH7.4	6.6	
Log D pH5.5	6.6	
T1/2 fish	2.32	days-1

	<i>Generic QSAR based COSMOS model Parameterization</i>	<i>from EuroMix M11/literature</i>
PCAir	3.42E9	1E99
PCFat	88.4	66.1
PCPoor	1.3	3.3
PCRich	76.6	4.4
PCLiver	7.6	6.1
PCSkin	1.3	7.7
PCSkin_sc	495 / 0.04 see text	0.12
Kp_sc_vs	0.75	0.1
Ke	0.07	0.01
CLH	0.16 days-1	n.a.
Fup	3.56E-5 / 0.01 see text	0.2
Frac	1	0.3
Kgut	3	1.3

Graphic comparison of the full parameterization (Milestone 11, WP7) of Cypermethrin with the QSAR generated (generic) parameterization is given in the following figure:

PBPK Cosmos parameterization Cypermethrin from Milestone 11 (x-axis) versus QSAR estimated (y-axis)

Overall the concordance between the QSAR estimates and the estimates from literature/experiment are very good. For comparison the 10-fold thresholds have also been indicated in the graph (as dotted lines), showing that most parameters are estimated within an order of magnitude (for cypermethrin). The exceptions are the estimate of the Partition coefficient skin-stratum corneum (PCskin_sc) and the fraction unbound in plasma (fup). With regard to the first parameter, the QSAR estimate is 495, where the value taken for parameterization in M11 was only 0.12. It should be noted that the estimate of the partition coefficient between skin and the stratum corneum in Milestone 11 is not based on experimental data, but on a very simple assumption, i.e. that $PC_{skin_sc} = PC_{skin} / PC_{fat}$. This approach is a huge simplification, and the QSAR used to estimate PCskin_sc ($PC_{skin_sc} = 0.72 * Kow(at\ pH5.4) ^ 0.43$) should in principle give a more realistic estimate of the true partition coefficient. If the approach from Milestone 11 is followed (dividing the PCskin from QSAR by the PCfat from QSAR) the estimate for the PCskin_sc would be 0.04, which is very close to the value used in Milestone 11, 0.12. Both values are indicated in the graph.

The second parameter deviating significantly from the parameterization given in Milestone 11 is the fraction unbound in the blood plasma (fup). The value estimated by QSAR is 3.6E-5 whereas the value from

M11 is 0.2, i.e the fraction unbound (free) in the blood plasm is 20%. The QSAR for fup is a sigmoid relationship with the octanol water partition coefficient (see following graph),

The problem is that extrapolation to the extremes of this relationship (log Kow values >5 or below -1) give extremely low (or high) values of the fraction unbound, approaching 0 (or 100)%, effectively making a substance with high log Kow completely not biologically available. Bracketing this function to e.g a minimum fraction unbound in the plasm of 1% (a value of 0.01), and subsequently a maximum of 99% (a value of .99) seems practical, to avoid too extreme behaviour. This is in effect what also is done in the IndusChemFate implementation of the QSARs. With an estimate of 0.01 for the fup parameter, the estimate is still more than a factor of 10 apart from the literature value, but comes (sufficiently) close to the 10-fold band indicating « within an order of magnitude difference ». The estimation QSAR of fup would then effectively have the same boundaries as defined in the Table with the relationships for Ke, the renal elimination rate.

The highly influential estimation of metabolism rate (CLH, clearance half life) can not directly be compared to the parameterization in Milestone 11, because the kinetic model in COSMOS is parameterized using Michaelis Menten kinetics, a (enzymatic) Vmax and Km value.

The estimation of metabolic rate using QSARs comes from a model derived from fish whole body clearance data, which is then allometrically scaled to rat. So we assume that liver from fish and rat are basically doing the same (and at the same rate) and only body weight and temperature need to be corrected for. This is a very crude assumption, and this might be improved upon in the near future.

Effectively, a QSAR model for human clearance rate, in analogy from the fish model, has been developed and published [Arnot, 2014]. The model is however not available in a software implementation, making application to new chemical structures difficult. It would be worthwhile, for the purpose of generic PBPK modelling, to create a software implementation of this human clearance rate model. This would currently cost too much time/capacity but might be an option in the remaining time of the EuroMix project. Contact with the authors has already been established and all background data has been assembled.

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Annex 1. Steatosis testing candidates

Proposed list of substances from the EuroMix Inventory, that are of interest for further testing of the Steatosis endpoint, based on QSAR/Molecular docking calculations.

Annex I – Proposed list of further testing Steatosis compounds.xlsx

Annex 2. EuroMix Inventory with all TTC, QSAR and Docking calculation results, and similarity rankings for the selections of Craniofacial Malformations testing candidates

Within the EuroMix inventory in this excel table, the columns identifying similarity to the substances identified in section 5.2 can be used to filter/sort the Inventory and produce short-lists of structural analogues to generate the proposed lists of substances of interest for further testing of the Developmental toxicity / craniofacial malformation endpoint.

Annex II – EuroMix inventory with all in silico calculation results.xlsx

Annex 3. EuroMix Steatosis Reference dataset

The final set of 207 compounds for which literature data is available on the occurrence of Steatosis as a phenotype of hepatotoxicity after repeated dose toxicity testing. The dataset is used to determine the predictive performance statistics of the 4 QSAR models that give information on steatosis as a phenotype, as well as the interpretation (threshold values for binding energy as well as predictive performance statistics) of the Molecular Docking calculation for the 16 Liver Nuclear Receptors involved in the AOP Steatosis.

Annex III - final set of 207 cmp val set STEATOSIS.xlsx